

Synthesis of 5,5'-Dichloro-3',3''-disulphanilylamido-phenolphthalein

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Sulphonamidochlorophthaleins have been synthesised with a view to studying their pharmacological properties. Phenolphthalein on nitration yields 3',3''-dinitrophenolphthalein which on chlorination, followed by reduction, provides 5,5'-dichloro-3',3''-diaminophenolphthalein. The latter on condensation with *N*-acetylsulphanilyl chloride (ASC) affords a product which on hydrolysis yields 5,5'-dichloro-3',3''-disulphanilylamidophenolphthalein.

Following the synthesis by van Kampen and Graafland¹ of 3',3''-disulphanilylamidophenolphthalein, which is found to be effective in bile-duct infections, Mehta and co-workers² have recently synthesised sulphonamidiodophthaleins. In view of the extensive use of chlorine-containing organic compounds, such as, chloroquine, chlorpromazine, phenoltetrachlorophthalein, etc. in medicine, sulphonamidochlorophthaleins have been synthesised to ascertain their pharmacological properties. A scheme of the reactions is shown below.

1. *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, 45, 3492
2. Mehta et al., *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, 30, 460.

EXPERIMENTAL

3', 3''-Dinitrophenolphthalein (II).—Phenolphthalein (I) was nitrated with a mixture of acetic and nitric acids at 10–15° to 3',3''-dinitrophenolphthalein (II), m. p. 198–99° (lit³, m. p. 196–97°).

5',5''-Dichloro-3', 3''-dinitrophenolphthalein (III).—Through a solution of (II) (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (150 ml) in a conical flask (250 ml) pure dry chlorine gas was bubbled till two equivalents of chlorine were absorbed. The reaction mixture after keeping overnight was poured into ice-cold water when a bright yellow precipitate separated. This was dissolved in 4% aqueous NaOH solution, treated with sodium sulphite, and filtered into 15% HCl, forming a precipitate of 5',5''-dichloro-3',3''-dinitrophenolphthalein (III) which on repeated washing with cold water melted at 103–105° (decomp.), yield 75–77%. (Found: C, 50.02; H, 1.87; N, 5.72; Cl, 14.87. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6N_4Cl_2$ requires C, 50.31; H, 2.10; N, 5.88; Cl, 14.89%.)

It is a bright yellow, amorphous powder, soluble in acetone and in chloroform, but sparingly soluble in ethanol. It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with an orange-red colour; it exhibits an orange-yellow colour with alkali and alkali carbonates and is completely reprecipitated by acids from the alkaline solutions.

5',5''-Dichloro-3',3''-diaminophenolphthalein (IV).—A fresh solution of sodium hydrosulphite (4.38 g.) in water (25 ml) was added with vigorous stirring to a solution of the preceding phthalein (III) (2g.) in hot acetone (100 ml). During reduction the colour of the reaction mixture changed from light yellow to straw-yellow. A blue colour formed on addition of NaOH solution to a little of the reaction mixture, when the reduction was complete. Brown solid, obtained by removal of acetone after dilution with water, was dissolved in 5% HCl and treated with 2% aqueous NaOH solution (pH 6.5–6.8) to obtain the product (IV), m. p. > 300°, yield 45–46%. (Found: C, 57.31; H 3.05; N, 6.59; Cl, 16.71. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_4Cl_2$ requires C, 57.55; H, 3.36; N, 6.72; Cl, 17.03%.)

It is a colorless, amorphous powder, soluble in ethanol and acetone and insoluble in ether. It dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates with a blue colour and is also soluble in H_2SO_4 (conc.).

3. Van Kampen, *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 8677.

5',5''-Dichloro-3',3''-diacetylsulphanilylamidophenolphthalein (VI).—To a solution of (IV) (2 g.) in a mixture of acetone (30 ml), ethanol (18 ml), and pyridine (3 ml) in a stoppered flask was added *N*-acetylsulphanilyl chloride (V) (2.24 g.) and the mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. The colour of the reaction mixture changed from deep yellow to red. On concentration and removal of pyridine, the mixture yielded a viscous liquid from which, on dilution with water, a light brown solid separated. All attempts to crystallise the product from most of the organic solvents did not succeed. Repeated treatment of the solid by dissolving in ethanol and precipitating it with water finally afforded the desired product (VI), m.p. 176-78° (decomp.), yield 50-55%. (Found: C, 53.12; H, 3.12; N, 6.79; Cl, 8.46; S, 7.76. $C_{36}H_{28}O_{10}N_4Cl_2S_2$ requires C, 53.27; H, 3.45; N, 6.91; Cl, 8.76; S, 7.89%).

It is a colorless amorphous powder, soluble in ethanol and acetone and insoluble in ether. It dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates, forming a deep blue solution. It is insoluble in HCl.

5',5''-Dichloro-3',3''-disulphanilylamidophenolphthalein (VII).—A solution of the preceding compound (VI) (1 g.) in 4% aqueous NaOH solution (20 ml) was heated at 100° for 2 hours. The solution, after cooling and diluting with water, was adjusted to pH 6.5-6.7 with 5% HCl when a bulky precipitate of the desired product (VII) was obtained. It could not be crystallised from most of the organic solvents. Its purification by repeated treatment by dissolving in ethanol and precipitating with water provided a white solid, m.p. 151-54° (decomp.), yield 65-70%. (Found: C, 52.56; H, 3.08; N, 7.52; Cl, 9.59; S, 8.97. $C_{32}H_{24}O_8N_4Cl_2S_2$ requires C, 52.82; H, 3.30; N, 7.70; Cl, 9.77; S, 8.80%).

It is a colorless amorphous solid, soluble in ethanol and acetone, but is insoluble in ether. It dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates, forming a deep blue solution and in acid with a yellow colour. When diazotised and coupled with β -naphthol in alkaline solution, it produced an orange-red colour.

The authors wish to acknowledge their grateful thanks to the College authorities for granting facilities in carrying out this work.